

Principles and Priorities for the Development of Teachers' Skills in Teaching Students Learning Strategies

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Abstract:

This article presents ideas on educational strategies included in the scope of modern forms of education, the compromise of teachers in helping students receive quality education, the role of teachers in developing the skills of independent work of a student, the ability of teachers to form new approaches and develop existing skills. Elementary, middle, and high school teachers were asked to complete an analysis of school subjects out of teacher-dependent variables. A key measure of a teacher's self-efficacy is their confidence and utilization of learning strategies in all subject areas.

Keywords: Learning methods, strategic approach, strategy, learning strategy, learner, professional development, pedagogical counseling.

Introduction

To mature as a person who has achieved success in an educational society, it is necessary to become an integral part of the lifestyle of actions such as acquiring knowledge and strengthening skills in the economy of their own needs. It is important that the teacher can give the beginner piont in the student's mind on time to regularly perceive the skill of working as a daily vital need. The school helps teachers to teach students learning strategies for the following purposes: reading and understanding the text, doing projects and written work, writing notes, managing time, organizing information, learning and remembering, conducting tests, solving a problem, and self-control.

Today, the practical harmonized educational activities of Science and technology in schools, as one of the requirements of modern education, require the use of innovative educational strategies so that

all students understand the same thing and form skills in their thinking. Depending on the point of view that the level of assimilation of pupils is not the same, it is necessary to pay special attention to the needs of each student. This process is based on the fact that educational activities organized on the principles of cooperation are not only explanatory but also show, be able to ask questions, relate to life, analyze the highest results, sum up physiological capabilities, etc.

In any type of Education, traditional, innovative, distance online, or independent types of education, the question of setting an academic goal for students and the formation of skills to create an individual trajectory of action that leads to this goal awaits their new solutions and proposals. It is also envisaged that they will make their way to the expected result and form self-stimulation skills.

Object and methods of research

Learning strategies are methods that students use to learn effectively, as well as an individual way of organizing and using certain skills to master content more effectively or perform other tasks in academic and non-academic settings. Learning strategies allow teachers to teach students how to learn, not specific content or skills. This will help pupils become an active participants in the educational process. In a strategic approach-based process, students do not receive information from the teacher and use assessment passively because they learn to take into account all aspects of the learning process. Such active use of learning strategies will help students develop skills, build self-confidence, and increase motivation in the learning process. The use of strategies helps in self-study and helps pupils take responsibility for education. The purpose of using learning strategies is to influence the motivational or mental state of the pupil and how they choose, acquire, organize, or integrate new knowledge.

Strategies are a means of active, self-involvement in educational subjects necessary for the development of communicative competence. It is also one of many conscious actions used by pupils to improve the process of obtaining, storing, remembering, and using new information.

Instructional strategy guidelines are principles, and strategies that facilitate the reading process by teaching pupils how to learn, how to solve problems, and how to use the information they have learned to achieve success. Learning strategies include learning to develop a reading plan to pass the exam, controlling the understanding of the content of the data, clarifying the teaching materials, and evaluating the results.

Pupils move from learning elementary skills to learning middle-class content, they face the demands of reading information from textbooks, lecture texts, self-management, and written essays, and expressing understanding in tests. And when they move to the upper classes, they begin to focus not on the topic, but on practice. They are expected to be more motivated to invest time and effort in solving tasks or problems. The motivational aspects of the strategic approach are intended to be ascetic in achieving functionally effective results. Learning strategies, when applied in practice, ensure that the pupil independently seeks the knowledge gained and invents new forms of learning based on strategies that are acceptable and adapted to him, regardless of the knowledge of the teacher.

There are many ways to classify learning strategies. Strategies can be divided into categories based on the study of cognitive, and metacognitive abilities. While most of the strategic approaches based on the educational process today are adapted for language learning, their use in teaching all subjects serves to reveal functional significance, providing a good basis for understanding the complexity of learning strategies. An approach based on actions aimed at knowing the content in terms of the trajectory of certain practices that underlie pre-class, class time, and post-class activities can be implemented in the following manifestations: Planning strategic individual learning style or positive learning strategy;

An experimental strategic approach is a methodological but flexible approach that transforms new data into an orderly system and constantly revises it;

Monitoring strategic approach-critical sensitivity to self-management and information use;

In the learning process, it is considered very important that the teacher is able to carry out a diagnostic analysis of the pupils' mastering abilities. The issue of preparing pupils for learning strategies from the point of view of improving the teacher's skills requires innovative proposals as a direction that awaits new solutions. The strategy is derived from the meaning of "a plan of action designed to achieve a long-term or common goal". Learning strategies are methods developed to improve the pupil's overall learning ability. Learning strategies are designed to help assimilate and remember learning content using resources such as ideas, memories, logical thinking, and emotions. Effective educational strategies help pupils of different types to improve their ability to memory and focus, improve their reading and writing skills, and improve their ability to solve problems. New manifestations of educational strategy the appearance in which pupils concentrate components such as self-development, promotion of independent education, the study of easy learning methods, and the discovery of ways to easily assimilate large volumes of information in terms of volume and quality over a certain period are assessed as a modernist method. Depending on which type of classification the pupil belongs to, special principles are established and entered into a new strategic phase. Personalized learning strategies will be a means to facilitate learning, enrich it more interesting, and achieve more effective results.

It is no secret that an educator who is an all-round adult, a master of his profession, also has little opportunity to convey information to one hundred percent of pupils. Based on the age, interests, physiological and psychological capabilities of pupils, a different approach with each pupil requires skill from the teacher and skills based on the principles of pedagogical management. Educational activities organized based on learning strategies refer to the teacher in this matter. The pupil focuses on the area in which he needs to improve himself, and the pupil learns by studying according to his speed. It is also sometimes assumed that adapting limited social causes to learning strategies based on creative approaches will give the expected results. Because, with the ethical paradigms of some pupils, the origin of the conditions that must be taken into account is also implied. Mutual social influences, a strategic approach planned from the beginning during communication, give positive results.

Principles and practice pupil in the center. These theoretical orientations address educational subjects based on the educational paradigm and close coaching relationships from an internal perspective, but most importantly, innate psychological needs (competence, control, and agency(heredity)) and ease of learning. The context that explains the need to involve responsibility for learning to be imposed on the pupil and at the same time motivated by the will to learn can be said to be the most effective view of controlling existing pupils. The relationship between the subjects of education justifies our hypothesis that the practices of caring supporting and feeling the presence of opportunities for the development of competence in areas important to the pupil become one of the basic principles of teaching using educational strategies.

Introduction of technology in the classroom: the effective use of tools such as an active educational strategy in educational institutions helps to develop live educational cooperation, and helps teachers prepare and improve lesson plans. The use of this technology in the classroom can be a valuable tool that prepares pupils to learn 21st-century skills. The use of presentations, videos, virtual hands-on lessons, robots, and extended data not only arouses interest in the classroom but also improves student collaboration and helps teachers achieve an effective learning environment that allows them to deliver information.

The general area of learning strategy comes from the entire pupil's view that pupils of all ages seek to find meaning in what they are learning and personally create their strategies when necessary or when action is necessary. [8; 7] The lack of mutual integration of theory and practice can lower the level of interest. Strategies that rely on creative freedom are based on the possibility of imagination and the creative approach, for example, the possibility of drawing or verbal observation of its imagination, formed based on learned education, which serves to strengthen knowledge.

Results and analysis

In today's globalized society, there are many ways to classify learning strategies. Based on the study of cognitive, metacognitive abilities, strategies can be divided into categories. While most of the strategic approaches based on the learning process today are tailored to language learning, their use in teaching all subjects serves to reveal the functional significance and provides a good basis for understanding the complexity of learning strategies. From the point of view of the trajectory of certain practices that lie based on pre-class, class time, and post-class activities, an action-based approach to knowledge of content can be carried out in the following manifestations:

Strategic approach planning-individual learning style or positive learning strategy;

An experimental strategic approach is a methodological but flexible approach that transforms new data into an orderly system and constantly revises it;

Monitoring the strategic approach-self-control and critical sensitivity to the use of information;

Behavioral learning strategies, on the other hand, include taking an example from others, drawing conclusions from trial and error, and seeking help . This type of education is related to the methods that the pupil uses for self-determination, which can conclude him/herself or others. Sometimes the reader has to share his/her thoughts about his thoughts. It is also important that they find other resources to improve their learning skills. Strategies for teaching good behavior consist of practical actions of particular importance for communication with materials and equipment required in many professional activities. Choosing a teacher learning strategy in the classroom is important for all pupils. How strategies are used by pupils and taught and supported by teachers makes grouping this learning strategy even easier. These strategies are sometimes revealed by teachers with concepts such as management skills and reading comprehension. Pupils do not always prefer a new style of study. It can be difficult to create solutions for learning tasks that are open to everyone in the entire class. According to researchers working in the field of education, the mixed-use of active learning strategies can help improve the academic performance of each pupil and help to understand them more deeply. Thus, it can be said that the best teaching methods for a teacher are a set of learning strategies that help pupils learn quickly and keep more in mind.

Focusing on pedagogy is a good starting point for any school with the highest impact. The teacher is advised to choose an educational strategy that best suits the current level of knowledge of pupils, the concept under study, and the level of knowledge of pupils.

Today, the practical harmonized educational activities of science and technology in schools, as one of the requirements of modern education, require the use of innovative learning strategies so that all pupils understand one thing and form skills in their thinking. Depending on the point of view that the level of assimilation of pupils is not the same, it is necessary to pay special attention to the needs of each pupil. Educational activities organized on the principles of cooperation are based not only on explanation, but also on the development of demonstration, interrogation, connection with life, analysis of the highest results, conclusion of physiological capabilities, etc. In any type of education, traditional, innovative, distance online or independent types of education, the issue of forming skills for pupils to set themselves an academic goal and create an individual trajectory of

action that leads to this goal awaits their new solutions and proposals. It is also envisaged that they will make their way to the expected result and form self-stimulation skills.

Conclusion

As a conclusion, it can be noted that peoples require a different approach due to the fact that they have different character-traits, psychological aspects. This situation requires an individual educational strategy for each pupil in the class. Pupils in the classroom can be gifted or super talented. By analyzing the high-performance abilities of children in what areas, effective approaches are determined depending on their intellectual, creative, artistic (visual and performing arts), leadership opportunities, or specific academic areas (natural, specific, social studies) and habits.

During this period, when the field of e-learning is rapidly developing, the reader receives the status of a user. This makes it easier to organize the e-learning activities based on learning strategies, analyze the results, and achieve the goal of assessment. Learning strategies ensure that the pupil independently seeks the knowledge gained and invents new forms of education based on optimal and self-adapted strategies, regardless of the teacher's knowledge. Failure to provide integration of theory and practice can reduce the interest of many pupils in science. Strategies that rely on creative freedom are based on the possibility of imagination and the creative approach, for example, the possibility of drawing or verbal observation of its imagination, formed based on learned education, which serves to strengthen knowledge.

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